

EMPLOYEE LEAVE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract. The primary objective of implementing this leave management system is to streamline the leave application process for employees, thereby enhancing their convenience and efficiency. By utilizing this system, employees can submit leave requests without unnecessary delays, ensuring a more seamless experience. Additionally, the system provides administrators with an easier and more efficient way to review and manage leave applications. This dual benefit underscores our commitment to improving operational efficiency and user satisfaction within the organization. The system is developed using PHP, HTML, CSS, jQuery and materialize CSS framework.

Keyword: leave, management, system, admin, employee

INTRODUCTION

The Employee Leave Management System (ELMS) is a comprehensive solution designed to streamline and automate the process of managing employee leave within an organization. This system addresses the complexities associated with traditional leave management methods, such as manual paperwork, inconsistent records, and inefficient approval workflows. By leveraging modern web technologies, ELMS provides an intuitive interface for employees to apply for various types of leave, including casual, sick, and maternal leave, while ensuring compliance with organizational policies and legal regulations [1].

PROBLEM

The manual management of employee leave requests presents several challenges for organizations. These challenges include time-consuming processes, a high potential for errors, and difficulties in tracking leave balances. Employees often face delays in leave approval, leading to dissatisfaction and inefficiency. It is also difficult to find leave histories and determine whether a leave request is valid and does not exceed the annual leave limit. This paper proposes an automated employee leave management system designed to streamline the leave request process, reduce errors, and improve overall efficiency [3]. By implementing this system, organizations can ensure timely leave approvals, accurate leave tracking, and better resource management.

APPROACH

This system consists of two roles. There are Administrator and Employee. Administrators receive notifications when employees submit leave requests, enabling timely review and decision-making. They can approve or reject leave applications based on the remaining leave balance and compliance with leave regulations. The system includes functionality for administrators to mark employees as inactive, thus restricting their access to the system. Additionally, administrators can manage job positions and view detailed leave statuses, including pending, approved, and rejected requests. The module also provides a comprehensive view of leave balances, helping administrators make informed decisions. Moreover, administrators have the ability to print records of employee numbers and the latest leave requests for better record-keeping and reporting.

The Employee module enables users to apply for leave, view their leave balances, review their leave history, change their passwords after logging in, and update their profiles. While the leave form is in pending state, employee has the option of cancelling it if they change their mind. This feature is aimed to better user experience. If an employee forgets their password, they can reset it using their employee ID and registered email. However, if an administrator marks an employee as inactive, that employee can no longer access the system. Employees cannot exceed the prescribed leave limits and leave rules for each leave type, ensuring compliance with organizational policies.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

ER diagrams consist of entities, which represent objects or concepts that can have data stored about them, and relationships, which illustrate how these entities interact with one another. Entities are typically depicted as rectangles, while relationships are shown as diamonds or lines connecting the entities. Attributes, which provide more details about the entities, are often represented as ovals linked to their respective entities. ER diagrams help in planning and designing a database by identifying the necessary tables and the relationships between them. It is a crucial tool in database design and helps in understanding the structure and relationships of data.

RESULTS

The implementation of an automated Employee Leave Management System (ELMS) offers numerous benefits to organizations. It significantly enhances operational efficiency by automating the entire leave request and approval process, reducing the time and effort required for manual handling. This automation minimizes human errors, ensures compliance with leave policies, and provides updates on leave balances, helping both employees and administrators make informed decisions. Additionally, the system fosters transparency and fairness, as employees can track the status of their leave requests and view their leave history. Notifications and alerts ensure timely responses to leave requests, improving overall communication and workflow [4]. The ELMS also supports administrative functions such as employee record management, leave type configuration, and role-based access control. Overall, the ELMS contributes to a more organized, efficient, and user-friendly leave management process, benefiting the entire organization.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

The Employee Leave Management System (ELMS) developed for the Highways Department has successfully automated the leave request process, making it more efficient and transparent. The system effectively handles employee leave applications, approvals, cancellations, and balance tracking. It has streamlined administrative tasks and reduced the workload associated with managing leave requests manually.

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